

Call for Papersa service provided by www.english.upenn.edu

search

[FAQ](#)[changelog](#)

[2025 \(/cfp/2025\)/02 \(/cfp/2025/02\)/04 \(/cfp/2025/02/04\)](#)

[flag as inappropriate \(/node/add/flag/100765\)](#)

CfP: Ecocritical Perspectives on Literature and Other Media (Lexington Books, U.K.)

deadline for submissions: May 15, 2025

full name / name of organization:

Habib Tekin / Istanbul and Marmara Universities

contact email:

habib.tekin@marmara.edu.tr (<mailto:habib.tekin@marmara.edu.tr>)

This call for papers seeks contributions examining the relationship between narratives and ecological issues, focusing on the ways storytelling addresses ecological challenges. Narratives – whether literary, cinematic, or multimodal – have the potential to critique environmental exploitation, envision sustainable futures, and explore human and non-human interconnections. The intersection of ecocriticism and storytelling offers fertile ground for discussions about the role of culture in shaping ecological consciousness and practices.

Submissions are encouraged from scholars in literary studies, environmental humanities, cultural studies, and related fields. Theoretical, comparative, and interdisciplinary approaches are welcome. We invite contributions that critically engage with the concept of ecology and storytelling, exploring the cultural, ethical, and aesthetic dimensions in the topics, including, but not limited to,

1. Ecocriticism, Ecofeminism
2. Ecological narratives
3. Sustainability narratives
4. Climate Crisis & Climate fiction
5. Eco poetics
6. Utopian/Dystopian narratives
7. (Post-)Apocalyptic narratives
8. Nautical Fiction
9. Plant Studies / Narratives
10. Animal Studies / Narratives
11. Gender Equality and Ecology

12. Ecology and Science Fiction
13. Ecology and Fantasy Fiction
14. Ecolinguistics
15. Ecosemiotics

Submission Guidelines

- **Manuscripts:** 6,000–8,000 words (including references)
- **Manuscript language:** English
- **Abstracts:** 250–300 words.
- **Formatting:** APA 7 citation style.
- **Abstract-Submission-Deadline:** 15.05.2025
- **Peer review:** Double-blind process.
- **Book Title:** Ecocritical Perspectives on Literature and Other Media
- **Publication:** Selected papers will be published as an edited volume under Lexington Books' Ecocritical Theory and Practice Series
- **Publisher:** Lexington Books

Please send your paper proposals (max. 1 DIN-A-Size, Times New Roman 12, 2000 characters including spaces) and a 100-word author biography till May 15, 2025 to the editors habib.tekin@marmara.edu.tr (<mailto:habib.tekin@marmara.edu.tr>), irem.atasoy@istanbul.edu.tr (<mailto:irem.atasoy@istanbul.edu.tr>) and okaradag@istanbul.edu.tr (<mailto:okaradag@istanbul.edu.tr>).

categories

[classical studies \(/category/classical-studies\)](/category/classical-studies)

[cultural studies and historical approaches \(/category/cultural-studies-and-historical-approaches\)](/category/cultural-studies-and-historical-approaches)

[ecocriticism and environmental studies \(/category/ecocriticism-and-environmental-studies\)](/category/ecocriticism-and-environmental-studies)

[interdisciplinary \(/category/interdisciplinary\)](/category/interdisciplinary)

[world literatures and indigenous studies \(/category/world-literatures-and-indigenous-studies\)](/category/world-literatures-and-indigenous-studies)

Last updated February 5, 2025

This CFP has been viewed 812 times.